

Supplementary Materials for

CNN-based surrogate for the phase field damage model: A study on its generalization across microstructure parameters for composite materials

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LIST OF DATASET

damage_prediction_A.zip Damage field predicted by the image-to-image(UNet) model and comparison with ground truth on the test set for dataset A.

damage_prediction_B.zip Damage field predicted by the image-to-image(UNet) model and comparison with ground truth on the test set for dataset B.

damage_prediction_C.zip Damage field predicted by the image-to-image(UNet) model and comparison with ground truth on the test set for dataset C.

damage_prediction_D.zip Damage field predicted by the image-to-image(UNet) model and comparison with ground truth on the test set for dataset D.

22 **damage_prediction_E.zip** Damage field predicted by the image-to-image(UNet) model and com-
23 parison with ground truth on the test set for dataset E.

24 **Vf20_R4.zip** Geometry image, resampled damage field images and peak load value calculated by
25 FEM for model training and test with volume fraction = 0.2 and fiber radii = 4 μm .

26 **Vf30_R4.zip** Geometry image, resampled damage field images and peak load value calculated by
27 FEM for model training and test with volume fraction = 0.3 and fiber radii = 4 μm .

28 **Vf40_R4.zip** Geometry image, resampled damage field images and peak load value calculated by
29 FEM for model training and test with volume fraction = 0.4 and fiber radii = 4 μm .

30 **Vf50_R2.zip** Geometry image, resampled damage field images and peak load value calculated by
31 FEM for model training and test with volume fraction = 0.5 and fiber radii = 2 μm .

32 **Vf50_R4.zip** Geometry image, resampled damage field images and peak load value calculated by
33 FEM for model training and test with volume fraction = 0.5 and fiber radii = 4 μm .

34 **Vf50_R6.zip** Geometry image, resampled damage field images and peak load value calculated by
35 FEM for model training and test with volume fraction = 0.5 and fiber radii = 6 μm .

36 **Vf20to50_R4.zip** Geometry image, resampled damage field images and peak load value calculated
37 by FEM for model training and test with volume fraction from 0.2 to 0.5 and fiber radii = 4
38 μm .

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TABLE S1. Hyperparameter study on the baseline model for peak load prediction

Initial channels	Number of Conv. Blocks	Channel numbers	RMSRE for peak load prediction
4	7	[1, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1]	0.0336 (Current)
8	6	[1, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1]	0.0298
16	5	[1, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1]	Out of memory
12	6	[1, 12, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1]	0.0321
2	8	[1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1]	0.187

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43 FEM, and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the
44 largest NRMSE on 6

45 S2 Dataset B: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by FEM,
46 and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the largest
47 NRMSE. 7

48 S3 Dataset C: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by FEM,
49 and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the largest
50 NRMSE. 8

51 S4 Dataset A: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by
52 FEM, and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the
53 largest NRMSE. 9

54 S5 Dataset E: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by FEM,
55 and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the largest
56 NRMSE. 10

57 S6 Comparison of the peak load calculated by FEM and predicted by (a) the image-
58 to-image-to-value surrogate model trained on the dataset with $V_f = 0.5$, $R_f = 2$ and
59 $4 \mu\text{m}$ (1000+1000 cases in total), and (b) the image-to-image-to-value surrogate
60 model trained on the dataset with $V_f = 0.5$, $R_f = 2, 4$ and $6 \mu\text{m}$ (1000+1000+10
61 cases in total), on the same test set with $V_f = 0.5$, $R_f = 6 \mu\text{m}$ (990 cases in total) to
62 study the extrapolation ability. 11

Fig. S1. Dataset A: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by FEM, and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the largest NRMSE on .

Fig. S2. Dataset B: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by FEM, and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the largest NRMSE.

Fig. S3. Dataset C: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by FEM, and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the largest NRMSE.

Fig. S4. Dataset A: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by FEM, and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the largest NRMSE.

Fig. S5. Dataset E: UNet model prediction of damage field, ground truth calculated by FEM, and their difference for the case with (a) the smallest NRMSE and (b) the largest NRMSE.

Fig. S6. Comparison of the peak load calculated by FEM and predicted by (a) the image-to-image-to-value surrogate model trained on the dataset with $V_f = 0.5$, $R_f = 2$ and $4 \mu\text{m}$ (1000+1000 cases in total), and (b) the image-to-image-to-value surrogate model trained on the dataset with $V_f = 0.5$, $R_f = 2, 4$ and $6 \mu\text{m}$ (1000+1000+10 cases in total), on the same test set with $V_f = 0.5$, $R_f = 6 \mu\text{m}$ (990 cases in total) to study the extrapolation ability.